

Pioneering AI in MLTC: Bridging Research & Practice

9th & 10th September 2024
Conference Handbook

On behalf of the AI for Multiple Long Term Conditions (AIM) programme, I'm delighted to welcome you to the Pioneering AI in MLTC: Bridging Research and Practice conference.

As lead investigator of the AIM Research Support Facility I'm honoured to work with so many kind, warm, and thoughtful experts in their fields. People from different professional backgrounds bringing together the necessary diversity of skills and knowledge to ensure people living with multiple long term conditions can thrive.

Our event showcases our principles of inclusive, collaborative team science. You'll join us in celebrating the power of involving members of the public, patients, and their family and carers in designing AI research. We'll share our learnings of how a better understanding of polypharmacy - the complexities introduced when clinicians provide medications to treat two or more concurrent conditions - can transform patient care.

AIM consortia have leveraged the UK's unique health data assets to catalyse AI research in multiple long term conditions. We'll share some of the challenges we have learned from over the last three years, and envisage new ways of working responsibly and effectively with sensitive data.

Our focus has always been on the impact of our research. Breaking down the ivory tower and using data and computational models to serve the people living with MLTCs. I am sure you'll be as inspired as I am as we celebrate the policy and industry innovations that are pushing at the boundaries of our current systems.

I want to particularly thank the early career researchers for joining us today, and for all their work. Without you there would be no research outputs. No one to review the missing data values or catch the bugs in the code. Your focus on working reproducibly, responsibly, and with integrity will change the world for the better.

Thank you all, and welcome,

*Dr Kirstie Whitaker
Programme Director for Tools, Practices and Systems
The Alan Turing Institute*

Acknowledgment

This conference wouldn't have been possible without the valuable input from the AIM community. We are particularly grateful for the work of the Programme & Operational committees, the AIM programme managers and contributors to the PPIE workshop. We would also like to thank the people who joined our regular town halls and drop-in session. We would like to highlight the following people:

Programme Committee including poster abstract review

- Mike Barnes
- Monica Fletcher
- Gareth Giles
- Thomas Jun
- Mario Moroso
- Naheed Tahir
- John Taylor
- Kirstie Whitaker
- Lynne Wright

Operational Committee

- Batool Almarzouq
- Sydney Ambrose
- Beth Collop
- Monica Fletcher
- Azimah Said

AIM Conference Patient & Public Involvement & Engagement workshop attendees

- Janice Connelly
- Emily Kylam
- Lynn Laidlaw
- Irene Poku
- Gillian Richards
- Jack Welch
- Farheen Yameen

AIM Programme Managers

- Angela Crawford
- Becky Birch
- Emilia Holland
- Glenn Simpson
- Emma Lo
- Rachael Wright
- Lucy McCloughan
- Nicola Pidduck
- Mary Logan
- Carly Flowers
- Michelle Miller

AI for Multiple Long-term Conditions
Research Support Facility

Programme
Day 1
Monday 9th September

Time & Chair	Title of Session	Session Description
09:30 - 10:15		Registration
10:15 - 10:35 Chair: Aziz Sheikh University of Oxford	The AIM Programme: Context, realisation and impact	Welcome from Chair Health Research & the Alan Turing Institute Aldo Faisal , Director of Science & Innovation, The Alan Turing Institute Overview of the AIM Programme & RSF - impact, key achievements and lessons learned Kirstie Whitaker , PI AIM RSF, The Alan Turing Institute
10:35 - 10:55	Interview	An interview by Aziz Sheikh with Professor Lucy Chappell , Chief Scientific Adviser to the Department of Health and Social Care and CEO of the NIHR (Live via video link)
10:55 - 11:25 Chair: Monica Fletcher University of Edinburgh	Celebrating and recognising excellence in Patient and Public Engagement and Involvement	Brief Introduction from Monica Fletcher Short Film from DECODE Panel Discussion Alix Glacier , PPIE contributor, DECODE Amy Wilkins , SLT - Researcher, DECODE John Taylor , PPIE contributor, CoMPuTE Lizzie Remfry , Early Career Researcher, AI Multiply
11:25 - 11:45	Comfort break	Tea & coffee break
11:45 - 12:45 Chair: Ronan Lyons Swansea University	Leveraging the UK's unique health data assets to catalyse AI Research in Multiple Long-term conditions	The AIM data journey – Challenges, Insights, lessons learnt Chris Orton , Head of Business Development, SeRP & SAIL Databank Through a glass, darkly: reflecting on data challenges in multiple long-term conditions research Bruce Guthrie , PI AIM CISC, University of Edinburgh New ways of working Puja Miles , Director CPRD (Clinical Practice Research Datalink) Building a UK data infrastructure at scale – Unifying Health Data in the UK, Review Cathie Sudlow , HDRUK (Health Data Research UK) Panel discussion Chris Orton , Bruce Guthrie , Puja Miles , Cathie Sudlow , Susan Mountain (PPIE contributor, AI Multiply)

Programme
Day 1
Monday 9th September

AI for Multiple Long-term Conditions
Research Support Facility

12:45 - 13:45 **Lunch** **Networking & poster viewing**

13:45 - 14:30

Chair:
Monica Fletcher
University of
Edinburgh

**Scaling up the
impact: Bridging
the gap between
research, policy,
people and
practice**

The Task Force for Multiple Long-Term Conditions.
Priority setting and progress to date | **Duleep Allirajah**,
CEO of the Richmond Group

Understanding the impact of multimorbidity and social
care need in England and Wales from the Cluster -AIM
study. | **Hajira Dambha-Miller**, PI Cluster AIM,
University of Southampton

Raising the Bar in Policy Research - Lessons learnt
from the NIHR Policy Research Unit in Healthy Ageing |
Jane McDermott, NIHR PRU Health Ageing, University
of Manchester

Lost in translation? Looking for the lived experience of
multiple long-term conditions in data | **Simon Fraser**, PI
MELD-B, University of Southampton & **Lynn Laidlaw**,
PPIE contributor MELD-B

Panel discussion
Duleep Allirajah
Hajira Dambha-Miller
Jane McDermott
Simon Fraser
Lynn Laidlaw

14:30 - 15:30

Chair:
Tony Avery
University of
Nottingham

**Using Real World
Data to identify and
plan interventions to
minimise
polypharmacy and
transform
prescribing in
Multiple Long term
Conditions**

A National perspective on polypharmacy | **Tony Avery**,
University of Nottingham

Sophisticated digital tools to support medication
reviews - barriers and facilitators to implementation in
NHS systems | **Lauren Walker** Co-PI DynAIRx,
University of Liverpool.

Exploring the burden of polypharmacy in multiple long
term conditions | **Mike Barnes**
Co-PI AI Multiply, Queen Mary University of London.

Utilising an Informatics consult to improve prescribing
| **Krish Nirantharakumar**
Co-PI OPTIMAL, University of Birmingham

Panel Discussion
Lauren Walker
Mike Barnes,
Krish Nirantharakumar
Alan Griffiths (PPIE Lead DynAirX)

Programme

Day 1

Monday 9th September

15:30 - 15:45	Comfort Break	Tea & coffee break
15:45 - 16:30	Pushing at the boundaries: Can AI, data science & digital innovation transform MLTC Health & Social Care research?	An Industry Perspective Rajat Desikan & Mario Giorgi , GSK Risk prediction and causal methods in a multi-morbidity context Matthew Sperrin , Senior Lecturer in Health Data Science, University of Manchester The future for AI Health Research in the UK Simon Thompson , Professor of Health Informatics, Swansea University, Co-Director, SAIL Databank Panel Discussion Matthew Sperrin Simon Thompson Rajat Desikan Mario Giorgi
16:30 - 16:45	Closing Session	Reflections of the day Aziz Sheikh
16:45 - 17:45	Networking time	Time for for individual research consortia to meet
17:45 - 19:00	Free time	Opportunity for hotel check-in
19:00 - 19:30	Dinner	Arrival at Browns Brasserie & Bar Manchester from 19:00 - 19:30, dinner served from 19:30 Browns Manchester 1 York Street Manchester M2 2AW

Programme
Day 2
Tuesday 10th September

AI for Multiple Long-term Conditions
 Research Support Facility

09:00 - 09:30	Title of Session	Registration
09:30 - 09:45	Welcome	Welcome and introduction to day 2 Kirstie Whitaker
09:45 - 10:15	Presentations	Lightening presentation for posters Chair: Kirstie Whitaker The Alan Turing Institute
		Alison Drewett , DECODE Simon Fraser , MELD-B Sam Relton , Dynairx Kieran Richards , AI Multiply Guillermo Romero Moreno , AIM CISC Chunyu Zheng , AIM CISC
10:15 - 11:00	How do we build trust for meaningful engagement?	Engaging with Representative Groups: Engaging patient communities in AI & MLTC research Panel Discussion Rashmi Kumar , PPIE contributor, CoMPuTE Stephanie Hanley , Research Fellow at the University of Birmingham, PPIE Community of Practice Alisha Angdembe , Researcher at Queen Mary University of London, AI MULTIPLY
11:00 - 11:15	Comfort Break	Tea & coffee break
11:15 - 12:00	Presentations	AIM presentations AIM CISC AI MULTIPLY Cluster AIM CoMPuTE
12:00 - 12:15	Comfort Break	Tea & coffee break
12:15 - 13:00	Presentations	AIM presentations DECODE Dynairx MELD-B OPTIMAL
13:00 - 14:15	Lunch	Networking and poster viewing

Programme
Day 2
Tuesday 10th September

AI for Multiple Long-term Conditions
Research Support Facility

14:15 - 15:15

**Collaborative
discussion**

Chair:
AIM RSF
NIHR (National
Institute of
Health Research)

Focussing on the future: how do we ensure impact through translation of your research to improve health & social care for MLTC patients, in the next 5 years?

Working together to address the challenges in AI for MLTC

1. How can we mobilise knowledge that has been generated by AIM?
2. What are the strategies & good practices for engaging and sustaining patient communities?
3. How can we champion early career researchers in MLTC research?
4. What technical support is needed for the next stage of translation/impact?
5. Who do we need to engage to ensure broad collaboration for translating research?
6. How would we move towards system thinking and transdisciplinary research in MLTC?

Breakout groups will be spread across Panorama, Survey & Outlook rooms.

15:15 - 15:30

Comfort Break

Tea & coffee break

15:30 - 16:00

**Feedback
opportunity**

Chair: NIHR
(National
Institute of
Health Research)

Breakout groups from the previous session presents discussion points, solutions and questions to the wider audience

16:00 - 16:15

Closing session

Reflections on the conference

Aziz Sheikh
Kirstie Whitaker

Speaker Bio's

Duleep Allirajah

Duleep Allirajah is Chief Executive of the Richmond Group of Charities, a coalition of 14 national health and care charities. Duleep has worked in policy and influencing roles, predominantly in the voluntary sector, for over 25 years. Prior to joining the Richmond Group, he was Assistant Director of Policy and Campaigns at the Royal College of General Practitioners (RCGP), where he led the development of Fit for the Future, the College's vision for the future of general practice. Duleep's previous roles include Head of Insight and Public Affairs at the Parliamentary and Health Service Ombudsman (PHSO) and Head of Policy at Macmillan Cancer Support. At Macmillan, he played a leading role in achieving policy change on a range of issues from hospital car parking and prescription charges to redesigning post-treatment care and support for cancer survivors.

Alisha Angdembe

Alisha Angdembe is a Data Scientist/Researcher at the William Harvey Research Institute, Queen Mary, University of London, specialising in AI applications for healthcare. Since 2021, she has worked on the AI-Multiply consortium, analysing large electronic health record datasets to understand long-term conditions and polypharmacy. Alisha collaborates with healthcare professionals, contributes to research publications, and engages with patients and public through workshops and meetings.

Tony Avery

Professor Tony Avery is National Clinical Director for Prescribing, a GP and Professor of Primary Health Care at the University of Nottingham. He is also a National Institute for Health Research (NIHR) Senior Investigator. He has led a number of major studies investigating the frequency, nature and causes of prescribing safety problems in the NHS. He has also developed effective methods for tackling hazardous prescribing, which has now been rolled out nationally to GP's in England. Tony's work recognises the vital role that medicines have in treating illness and helping people live with long-term conditions, while acknowledging that prescribing of a medicine is not always the best solution. He is committed to ensuring health care professionals and patients have the information and support they need for shared decision making about whether a prescription is needed and, if so, how to balance the effectiveness and safety of medicines alongside the costs to the patient, the NHS and the environment.

Mike Barnes

Professor Michael Barnes leads the Centre for Translational Bioinformatics (C4TB) at QMUL. His team work across many disciplines, including genomics, drug discovery, stratified medicine, high performance computing, machine learning and artificial intelligence and health informatics with a unified objective to drive forward translation into the clinic. Michael is a member of the QMUL Digital Environment Research Institute faculty, and is an HDR-UK Investigator. He is co-PI on the AI-Multiply consortium which used AI to investigate the interplay between multimorbidity and polypharmacy. He is also co-investigator on several MRC stratified medicine projects, including MRC PSORT (Psoriasis), MRC RA-Map (RA), MRC MATURA (RA) and MRC CLUSTER (Juvenile Idiopathic Arthritis). He has served on a range of funding panels for the MRC, NIHR, BBSRC, EPSRC and has also contributed to several project advisory boards.

Speaker Bio's

Lucy Chappell

Professor Lucy Chappell is the Chief Scientific Adviser for the Department of Health and Social Care (DHSC), with overall responsibility for the department's research and development, including the National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR). Professor Chappell is Professor of Obstetrics at King's College London, Honorary Consultant Obstetrician at Guy's and St Thomas' NHS Foundation Trust and an NIHR Senior Investigator.

**Hajira
Dambha-Miller**

Dr Hajira Dambha-Miller is a GP and leads the cross-faculty Data Science Research group. She has an interest in large-scale epidemiology studies that can inform preventive action. She works across a range of clinical topics but particularly around the prevention of chronic disease and Multiple Long Term Conditions (multimorbidity). Her studies use primary care electronic health records including CPRD, SAIL, Q-Research, ELSA, CHIA and international datasets in Canada and the USA. She has also curated a number of novel datasets linking health, social and environmental data. She currently leads a programme of work funded by the NIHR to examine clusters of disease in people with Multiple Long-Term Conditions using health and social care electronic records (AIM-study). Hajira co-leads the methodologies workstream for the NIHR cross collaboration in Multiple Long Term Conditions. She has previously established and chaired the COVID-19 Big Data National Group, and is a member of the International Monitoring Mortality Inequality Consortium. She is an honorary fellow at the MRC Epidemiology at the University of Cambridge. She has provided evidence to Government ministers on big data methods and their interpretation, and is also editor-in-chief of the British Journal of General Practice Open.

Rajat Desikan

Dr Rajat Desikan is a computational biologist with 11 years of diverse research experience. He is the director for Clinical Pharmacology Modelling and Simulations, at GSK, involved in the development of several early and late stage clinical assets. Core expertise is in computational and quantitative systems pharmacology modelling within the therapeutic areas of infectious diseases, vaccines, and immunology.

Aldo Faisal

Professor Aldo Faisal is the Professor of AI & Neuroscience at the Dept. of Computing and the Dept. of Bioengineering at Imperial College London. In 2021 he was awarded a prestigious 5-year UKRI Turing AI Fellowship. In 2019, Aldo became the founding director of the £20Mio UKRI Centre for Doctoral Training in AI for Healthcare and leads the Behaviour Analytics Lab at the Data Science Institute, London. Aldo works at the interface of Machine Learning, Neuroscience and translational Biomedical Engineering to help people in diseases and health. He currently is one of the few engineers worldwide that lead their own clinical trials to validate their technology. In this space, his works focus on Digital Biomarkers and AI for medical intervention (Makin et al, Nat Biomed Eng; Komorowski et al, NatMed, 2018; Gottessmann et al NatMed, 2019). His work has received several prizes and awards, including the \$50,000 Research Discovery Prize by the Toyota Foundation.

Speaker Bio's

Monica Fletcher

Chief Executive of the Centre for Applied Respiratory Research, Innovation and Implementation. Partnerships & Sustainability Lead on a range of large grants focussed on digital and data & AI innovations in health, including AI-MLTC. She has worked for large pharma as a Global Respiratory Medical Expert. As CEO of Education for Health, for over 17 years, she focussed on education and research in long term conditions. She has held various positions including Chair of the European Lung Foundation, Chair of the UK Inhaler Group. Monica has wide experience of advocacy from a National, European and Global level through a variety of senior leadership positions.

Simon Fraser

Professor Simon Fraser is Professor of Public Health and Deputy Head of School (Research) in the School of Primary Care, Population Sciences and Medical Education in the Faculty of Medicine at the University of Southampton, UK. His background and training is in both public health and primary care. His research aims to understand the determinants, burden, inequalities and adverse outcomes associated with long-term conditions. He leads a cross-disciplinary group of researchers investigating the prevention of burdensome multimorbidity across the lifecourse as part of the MELD-B study, one of the NIHR AIM programme research consortia. He also has a specific interest in kidney disease, has contributed extensively to work on kidney health inequalities, and leads research on the health-related quality of life among people living with chronic kidney disease.

Mario Giorgi

Dr Mario Giorgi is an Associate Director in Quantitative Systems Pharmacology (QSP) at Sosei Heptares with several years of experience in R&D, pharmaceutical consulting (worked with Roche, Pfizer, Astella, Genentech, Novartis) and project development. The most recent recognition of the impact of my work is the Certara's COVID19 vaccine simulator, winner of the R&D100 award in science and technology, and the 2022 Edison award in therapeutic impact (links below). He is currently a Director for GSK, a global biopharma company with a purpose to unite science, technology and talent to get ahead of disease.

Alix Glacier

Alix is a Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) member in the DECODE project. She has been part of DECODE for around 2 years. Alix is involved in other learning disability initiatives, such as the LEDER programme which looks into the lives and deaths of people with learning disabilities. Alix is also part of the Leicestershire Learning Disability Partnership Board and Locality Group where she is the chair of the group and leads meetings for both of them.

Speaker Bio's

Alan Griffiths

Alan lives in St Helens with his wife and son Christopher, who has a severe learning disability, epilepsy, autism, and type 2 diabetes. Alan is a retired Civil Engineer and worked in Urban Regeneration during Merseyside's Objective One programme. He was a Trustee of Royal Mencap Society when they ran a campaign called 'Death by Indifference' which highlighted that people with a Learning Disability suffer from massive Health Inequalities. He is a PA with ARC NWC, a member of their Health Inequalities sub group, Co-Lead of their Person Centred Complex Care theme, the Governance Sub Committee and PPIE Lead, having been co-applicant for their DynAIRx project. Outside of ARC Alan is a Member of the Cheshire and Merseyside NHSE Transforming Care Strategic Board (for people with a Learning Disability and/or Autism) and their Steering Group for LeDeR (the LD mortality review). He is also a PA on the SPHR HI sub group and was involved in developing the FOREquity web site.

Bruce Guthrie

Professor Bruce Guthrie is Professor of General Practice at the University of Edinburgh where he is the Director of the Advanced Care Research Centre and PI for the AIM CISC programme. He is a health services researcher using mixed quantitative and qualitative methods to understand and improve the quality and safety of healthcare, with a focus on multimorbidity, polypharmacy and prescribing quality and safety. He has led a number of projects in the field of multimorbidity including HDR-UK work examining how multimorbidity is measured in the research literature, and additionally collaborates with colleagues in the UK and internationally. To ensure implementation of research findings in the NHS, he has served on a number of national committees including chairing the Guideline Development Group for the NICE Multimorbidity clinical guideline, and being a member of the NHS Scotland Polypharmacy Working Group.

Stephanie Hanley

Dr Stephanie Hanley is a Research Fellow working on the MuM-PreDiCT project. Her research focuses on pregnancy and postpartum care, working in collaboration with women and staff. She has skills in qualitative and quantitative research and analysis, and co-designing research with service users. Stephanie is the Principal Investigator for a Medical Research Council grant focused on patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE). She is also involved in the PPIE Community of Practice, which, together with the AI for Multiple Long Term Conditions Research Support Facility, hosts informal and supportive sessions. These sessions provide a space for staff, early career researchers, clinicians, and public members to connect, share ideas, and collaborate on PPIE work across diverse communities within multiple long-term condition research.

Emma Karoune

Dr Emma Karoune works as a Senior Researcher focusing on Research Community Building in the Tools, Practices and Systems Programme. She brings her open research and community-building skills to projects including People in Data, the AI for multiple long term conditions research support facility, the Clinical AI Interest Group, the Turing-RSS Health Data Lab, the DECOVID project and Scoping the future of Health-AI. She is the Deputy Lead of the Research Community Management team within the Tools, Practices and Systems Research Programme. Emma is working closely with the Turing Skills Team to lead a project on Professionalising traditional and modern data science roles. This project is funded by a Skills Policy Award. She also co-lead People in Data that aims to convene an open community of data professionals, which promotes a culture that values and prioritises data and recognises people that work in data roles as essential to research. Emma is a Software Sustainability Institute Fellow focusing on promoting a more accessible and inclusive research culture. She is also working with Elixir-UK as a FAIR Data Stewardship Training Fellow to develop training resources for FAIR data management. Emma works closely with the Open Life Science Programme as a mentor and expert.

Speaker Bio's

Rashmi Kumar

Rashmi Kumar is an expert-by-experience and carer to family members with serious multiple long term health illness. As a carer he has direct experience of physical and emotional challenges patients and loved-ones face every day and how with little support their physical and psychological wellbeing can be significantly improved, enabling them to make positive contributions in their communities. Rashmi joined the MLTC team to learn and help share his lived experiences to improve relevance and deliverability of the MLTC work.

Rashmi has worked with policy makers, commissioners and many voluntary, community and social enterprise organisations (VCSE), as a Trustee of Patients Participation Group (PPGs) Network engaging with Primary Care Networks (PCNs), Community Groups and Integrated Care Boards.

Lynn Laidlaw

Lynn lives with a rare disease and multiple long term conditions. She is an experienced patient and public contributor and peer researcher, involved with multiple researchers, academic institutions and organisations across the U.K. She is particularly interested in co production and has experience of co producing evidence synthesis and qualitative research. She is a member of the PPI advisory board for the MELD-B project.

Ronan Lyons

Professor Ronan Lyons, OBE, FMedSci, MAE, MD is Professor of Public Health at Swansea University. He co-led the development of anonymised total population cohorts in the SAIL Trusted Research Environment as a platform for evaluating population and individual level interventions and policies. Professor Lyons has held many senior roles. Currently, he is principal investigator of the Medical Research Council (MRC) funded 'Controlling COVID-19 through enhanced population surveillance and intervention (Con-COV): a platform approach' and 'Application of machine learning to discover new multimorbidity phenotypes associated with poorer outcomes' collaborations. He is also Associate Director for the MRC's Dementias Research Platform UK, bringing together multi-modal data on many cohorts, and a senior investigator in the Economic and Social Research Council funded Administrative Data Research Wales Partnership.

Professor Lyons is particularly interested in the neglected field of injury prevention and control and is involved in many of the world's largest observational, interventional and policy relevant injury research studies. Since 2012, he has chaired the US National Centres for Health Statistics' International Collaborative Effort on Injury Statistics and Methods.

Jane McDermott

Jane is based within the NIHR Policy Research Unit in Healthy Ageing where she leads on strategic and operational priorities to support collaborative partnerships, public and community involvement and engagement, knowledge mobilisation, and impact. Working within, and across, an extensive network of health and social care policy and practice ecosystems, Jane draws upon 25+ years of experience of programme and project leadership, strategic relations, and impact in the fields of health ageing, policy influencing and social inclusion. Her work spans local, regional, national and international landscapes, and is underpinned by a life long commitment to equality, diversity, inclusion and belonging.

Speaker Bio's

Susan Mountain

Susan Mountain is from South Shields. She is an avid campaigner for a smoke-free Britain and has spoken at parliament a number of times to lobby for a tobacco bill which protects young people from smoking. Susan became involved as a PPI in research when she was asked to be part of tobacco research in 2017. She has since been involved in a lot of tobacco researches as well as health researches. She is on the steering group and programme board for the Secure Data Environment in North East and Cumbria, while also being on the NICE diagnostic advisory committee for Melanoma. Susan is also involved in the AI Multiply PPI management team where she leads on Early Career Researcher sessions and attends the Data Management sessions. She is passionate about research and how it is shaped and firmly believe in public involvement.

Puja Myles

Dr Puja Myles is Director of the UK Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency's (MHRA) specialist real world data research service, Clinical Practice Research Datalink (CPRD). She trained as a public health specialist and epidemiologist following her initial clinical training and practice as a dentist. She was a public health academic working with real world data for many years before she joined CPRD. She is a fellow of the Faculty of Public Health (UK), a senior fellow of the Higher Education Academy (UK) and holds a PhD in Epidemiology. Her current research areas include real world data research, data quality, synthetic data and in silico trials.

**Krish
Nirantharakumar**

Professor Krish Nirantharakumar is the theme lead for health informatics and Professor in Health Data Science and Public Health at the University of Birmingham. Krish's research interest spans across methodology development in epidemiology to clinical research in diabetes, endocrinology and multimorbidity. Krish's unique innovative methodological programme of work, known as "Automated Clinical Epidemiology Studies (ACES)", has led to the University of Birmingham gaining an international reputation for being one of the few universities globally to have successfully researched and knowledge-engineered epidemiological study designs into computer executable formats. Krish's team also emulate clinical trials rapidly, with one such study informing the largest data driven clinical trial to be funded by the National Institute for Health Research (DaRe2THINK), in which Krish is a co-investigator and the team lead for data co-ordination and management. Krish's team have demonstrated use of the ACES platform to answer clinical questions that arise during patient consultations within hours (Informatics Consult). Following this piece of work Krish (Joint Principal Investigator) and colleagues have obtained a grant from NIHR to develop an AI driven advanced patient similarity tool (OPTIMAL) to improve care for people with multiple long term conditions.

Chris Orton

Chris Orton is a Programme Manager based within Population Data Science at Swansea University Medical School. Chris currently manages Theme 1 within the RSF: Reproducible, secure, and interoperable infrastructure for the AI for Multiple Long-Term Conditions: Research Support Facility, ensuring that AIM consortia and wider researchers are supported in using research infrastructure such as Trusted Research Environments, and that methods and architectures in deploying research infrastructure are developed and disseminated.

Chris leads other research and infrastructure development initiatives at Swansea University, such as the SAIL Databank role within National Core Studies, the technical elements of the Health Data Research UK Inflammation and Immunity Driver Programme, and the legacy projects of the BREATHE Health Data Research Hub for Respiratory Health.

Speaker Bio's

Lizzie Remfry

Lizzie is a PhD student at Queen Mary University of London. Her research focuses on exploring trajectories of long-term conditions utilising epidemiological and machine learning methods, whilst embedding patient and public involvement and engagement at every step of the way.

Aziz Sheikh

Professor Sir Aziz Sheikh OBE is Nuffield Professor of Primary Care Health Sciences and incoming Head of the Nuffield Department of Primary Care Health Sciences at the University of Oxford. He is Professorial Fellow at Harris Manchester College, University of Oxford and Honorary Consultant with the UK Health Security Agency. He was previously Chair of Primary Care Research and Development, Director of the Usher Institute and Dean of Data at the University of Edinburgh. He has played important advisory roles to a number of governments, inter-governmental bodies, including the World Bank, World Health Organization and the World Innovation Summit for Health, and leading scientific bodies including the Academy of Medical Sciences and the Royal Society. He is a fellow of nine learned societies and has been awarded numerous UK and international awards for his work.

Aziz was made an Officer of the Order of the British Empire for 'Services to Medicine and Health Care' in 2014 and a Knight Bachelor in 2022 for 'Services to COVID-19 Research and Policy'.

Cathie Sudlow

Professor Cathie Sudlow is Director of the UKRI/MRC's Adolescent Health Study (AHS), a longitudinal population study and data platform focusing on critical biological/social developments that occur during adolescence. She holds a strategic advisory role within HDRUK and is Chair of Neurology and Clinical Epidemiology at the University of Edinburgh. Previously, Cathie was Chief Scientist and Deputy Director of HDR UK and Director of the BHF Data Science Centre. Other previous roles include Director of the Centre for Medical Informatics, Usher Institute, University of Edinburgh, the first Research Director for HDR UK Scotland and Chief Scientist of UK Biobank. Cathie's clinical work focused mainly on the assessment and treatment of patients with suspected stroke. Cathie holds Fellowships of the Academy of Medical Sciences and the Royal Society of Edinburgh. She was awarded an OBE for services to medical research in 2020.

Matthew Sperrin

Dr Matthew Sperrin is a senior lecturer in health data science at the University of Manchester. With a background in statistics, he has broad interests in methodology for prediction and causal inference in healthcare, and particularly the intersection of the two. He is a co-investigator on the DynAIRx project (using AI to support medicine optimisation in patients with multiple long term conditions), and involved with a range of other projects including the Causality in Healthcare AI hub (CHAI hub).

Speaker Bio's

John Taylor

John started his career in the Pathology Departments of the Bolton Hospitals Group, following qualifying he moved into a Consultancy specialising in Microbiological Quality Control in various industries. With a friend, he started a business producing specialised anti bacterial detergents for the brewing industry.

Some years later he suffered an MI resulting in quintuple CABGs repeated twice more at 8 year intervals, while also being diagnosed with having CKD resulting in a Left Renal Artery bypass graft, and severe Spinal problems.

John became involved in Medical Research through being invited to contribute to the Summary Care Records development, following which he was invited to join a Research Project. John has also worked with the NIHR reviewing Research Grant applications, where he has now reviewed over 30 applications.

Over the years, John has become involved in various healthcare and industrial fields and has also become a member of the MLTC patients, while being an active member of CoMPuTE's PPIE research team.

John's interest in Medical Research is strongly linked to his personal experiences and the knowledge that without the benefits of previous research he probably wouldn't have survived his health history.

Simon Thompson

Professor Simon Thompson is professor of Health Informatics and the senior technical academic for all data research investments in Swansea University. He is a systems architect with many years' experience in the NHS and academia. He is the Chief Technology Officer of a large team of talented and diversely skilled software developers, data innovation specialists and enterprise architecture engineers. Simon leads the innovation, design, development and implementation of all SeRP technical system developments. He is responsible for delivering the technical workstream for Swansea University as part of multiple UK networks of health and administrative data research centres of excellence and international collaborations.

Lauren Walker

Dr Lauren Walker is Reader in Clinical Pharmacology & Therapeutics and Honorary Consultant in General Internal Medicine. She co-leads the DynAIRx programme, funded by the NIHR AI in multimorbidity stream and her research interest involves utilising existing health record data to understand how multiple long-term conditions, and their associated prescriptions, evolve over time and how these relationships between drugs and diseases lead to harm. She is also the Academic Director at the NIHR Clinical Research Facility at Liverpool University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust and co-director of the Liverpool Early Phase Hub at the University of Liverpool.

Speaker Bio's

Kirstie Whitaker

Dr Kirstie Whitaker is a passionate advocate for making science "open for all" by promoting equity and inclusion for people from diverse backgrounds. She leads the Tools, Practices and Systems research programme at The Alan Turing Institute, the UK's national institute for data science and artificial intelligence. Kirstie founded and co-leads The Turing Way, an openly developed educational resource that enables researchers and citizen scientists across government, industry, academia and third sector organisations to embed open source practices into their work. She is the lead investigator of the £3 million AI for Multiple Long Term Conditions Research Support Facility, co-lead investigator for the AutSPACES citizen science platform, and co-investigator of the Turing's Data Safe Haven projects. Kirstie is the chair of the Turing's Research Ethics Panel and leads a diverse team of research application managers and research community managers who build open source infrastructure to empower a global, decentralised network of people who connect data with domain experts. She holds a BSc in Physics from the University of Bristol, an MSc in Medical Physics from the University of British Columbia, and a PhD in Neuroscience from the University of California at Berkeley. Kirstie joined the Turing as a Turing Research Fellow in 2017 after a postdoctoral fellowship at the University of Cambridge in the Department of Psychiatry. She is a Fulbright scholarship alumna and was a 2016/17 Mozilla Fellow for Science.

Amy Wilkins

Amy is a Speech and Language Therapist working in the DEOCDE project. The DECODE project aims to improve health outcome for adults with learning disabilities. Amy is one of the co-patient and public involvement leads and runs 4 PPI groups for people with learning disabilities and carers. Her role also includes supporting the research team to communicate with participants by making information accessible.

Abstracts

Hotspots of Multiple Long-Term Conditions in Wales.

Authors: Eleojo Abubakar, Chunyu Zheng, Alan Marshal, Chris Dibben, Jamie Pearce and Bruce Guthrie - AIM CISC

Abstract

High-risk areas of health conditions or other phenomenon of interest are known as spatial clusters or hotspots. The elicitation of hotspots of MLTCs can facilitate geographic targeting and monitoring of pertinent interventions and resource allocation. The objective of this study is to uncover localities at high risk of MLTCs in Wales by 2011. To this end, the age- and sex-standardised prevalence of MLTCs in Lower Super Output Areas were estimated and mapped from Electronic Health Records in SAIL. Thereafter, we detected hotspots of MLTC using Local Indicators of Spatial Autocorrelation, such as the local Moran's I and Geary's C. Our results characterise the spatial prevalence of MLTCs in neighbourhoods in Wales. Localities with a significantly high risk of MLTCs were also identified and mapped. The identified high-risk areas indicate neighbourhoods that should be prioritised by public health authorities for intervention activities.

INCIGRAPH: an interactive graphical tool for exploring the accumulation of MLTCs across demographics in CPRD GOLD.

Author: Marco Canducci - OPTIMAL

Complex Multi-Morbidity (cMM), or the accumulation of Multiple Long-Term Conditions (MLTCs) throughout a lifetime can complicate a patient's clinical picture. From a practitioner's perspective, the decision on a treatment can be influenced by not only the patient's history, but also the expected incidence of conditions for the patient's corresponding demographics (age, sex, ethnicity and deprivation). A better understanding of incidental combinations of long-term conditions across different demographics could partially alleviate a practitioner's job. It would also serve as a solid ground for policy-making strategies tailored to the prevention of discovered sequences of conditions for given population samples. We present INCIGRAPH, a graphical, interactive tool, designed to query incidence rates of all detected sequences of up to three long-term conditions, within a selection of 63 diseases. The tool should be used to study the incidence rates of specific sequences of conditions for combination of demographics. The most complicated question that can be explored via INCIGRAPH is: "What is the rank of these 63 diseases as first (second, third) to be contracted by a White (Black, Asian, Mixed or other ethnicity), Male (or Female) individual within 31 to 40 years old (0 to 90), given his/her deprivation index?" The user is encouraged by the intuitive graphical interface to explore the incidence of different diseases as they progress on an accumulation trajectory, in order to envision the most likely paths of complex multi-morbidity.

Approximate Bayesian Computation Inference of Rates of Multiple Long-Term Condition Accrual

Authors: L V Coutts, M Shiranirad, R Chiovloni, S D S Fraser, J Enright and R B Hoyle - MELD-B

Individuals with multiple long-term conditions (LTCs) acquire multiple diagnoses over their lifetime. Understanding how risk of future diagnoses is related to diagnosis history, for example the number, order and timing of past diagnoses, could aid clinicians in assessing risk of further diagnoses for individuals. However, for multiple LTCs, extracting such information from real world datasets is a complex task.

Here we aim to infer how rates of new diagnoses depend on diagnosis history, using both individual-based and compartmental models of patient diagnosis histories that we fit to electronic health record (EHR) data and using Approximate Bayesian Computation (ABC) to estimate the posterior distributions of diagnosis rates in the model.

Abstracts

The feasibility of using ABC for this task was assessed by fitting to EHR diagnosis history for five cardiac-related health conditions from a defined SAIL databank cohort.

Rates of diagnosis were inferred using ABC by modelling acquisition of one or more of the five conditions between 50 and 65 years of age and fitting to the total number of diagnoses in the cohort for each condition for each age. We consider distinct diagnosis rates that depend on individual's previous diagnoses, the order they acquired them and the patient's age. This results in a large number of model parameters to infer, so we treat certain diagnosis rates as fixed (derived empirically from EHR data or estimated using established clinical risk tools such as QRISK) and aim to infer the remainder. Diagnosis rates extracted from EHR data were approximately linear with age and depend on order of diagnosis. When employing a simple linear approximation, ABC was able to successfully infer modelled rates of diagnosis, to within a mean error of 6% of the true diagnosis rates.

In future work we plan to extend the model to include accrual of burden and other LTCs.

 This abstract was selected for a lightning talk by the Conference Programme Committee

Animated storytelling as a novel approach to communicating health information to people with learning disabilities.

Authors: Alison Drewett, Ellie Harvey, Navjot Kaur, Panos Balatsoukas, Sarah Rabbitte and Amy Wilkins, Thomas Jun, and Satheesh Gangadharan - DECODE

Nearly a third of people with learning disabilities (PWLD) have six or more multiple long-term health conditions (MLTCs), and they die twenty years younger than their non-learning-disabled counterparts. The DECODE research has identified the most frequent pairings and common MLTC trajectories (temporal sequences and duration) of chronic health conditions for PWLD. A key challenge is communicating these research findings to PWLD, who generally have lower health literacy than the general population. This necessitates creative approaches to accessibility in health information and public engagement.

This paper draws upon the development of an animated story, 'Maria's Story', designed to convey DECODE's findings. The 2-minute 42-second animation, based on a common MLTC trajectory and lived experiences, was co-created with PWLD through five participatory focus groups and engagement with public and patient involvement (PPI) groups. These sessions identified user requirements, tested prototypes, and evaluated iterations of storyboards, voiceover, and visual aspects such as colour, font, and imagery.

Seven design principles were identified in the research: addressing the heterogeneous nature of learning disabilities, avoiding cognitive overload, accommodating attention differences, allowing for literal understanding, maintaining meaningfulness and personalisation, considering emotional affect, and numerical literacy. The principles are a foundation for conversations about how best to design health communication for people with learning disabilities rather than universal statements.

The paper offers insights into effective visual communication for this population, emphasising that tailored imagery is not merely supplementary to written language, but it is valuable in its own right. It illustrates these insights with examples from 'Maria's Story' and demonstrates how complex numerical health data can be transformed into accessible content for PWLD. We argue that animated storytelling can enhance the interest, understanding and retention of health information for PWLD potentially improving health literacy and outcomes in this vulnerable population.

Abstracts

 This abstract was selected for a lightning talk by the Conference Programme Committee

Public policy which eases the personal financial impact of living with multiple long-term conditions

Authors: Simon DS Fraser, Jack Welch, James McMahon, Sally Dace, Lynn Laidlaw, Robin Poole, Luke Chandaman, Becky Wilkinson, Kelly Cheung, Jaskiran Kaur Gill, Chandni Jacob, Nisreen Alwan - MELD-B

Background

The Multidisciplinary Ecosystem to study Lifecourse Determinants and Prevention of Early-onset Burdensome Multimorbidity (MELD-B) study included a qualitative evidence synthesis on the everyday life impact for people living with multiple long-term conditions (MLTCs). This research highlighted eight key themes, one of which was financial impact. The aim of this work was to identify current Government policies that address the financial impact of living with MLTCs.

Method

A financial policy synthesis was undertaken and a policy brief aimed at policy makers and a plain English version were then co-authored by a member of the MELD-B Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) advisory group and a member of the academic team. Anonymised quotes depicting lived experience relating to financial challenges were provided by PPIE members and included in the policy briefs.

Results

Three key personal financial areas were identified which impact on people living with MLTCs – income deprivation, medication costs and appointment costs. Financial support for people living with MLTC is limited and no financial policies have been developed that specifically provide for people living with MLTCs. Barriers of entry, administrative work, and inadequacy in the extent of support they offer all impact people living with MLTCs negatively.

Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

The UK Government should work to reform and reduce the administrative burden of the current range of policies that provide financial support for people living with MLTCs and ensure equity for those digitally excluded. Co-production with people living with MLTCs should be actively embedded in policy development relating to financial impact on people accessing or utilising healthcare and of those requiring state benefits. Health and care services, in partnership with NHS Integrated Care Systems, should support policies to optimise the number of healthcare appointments for people living with MLTCs, thereby addressing fragmented pathways and reducing financial burden.

A knowledge-graph approach to predict adverse events from electronic health records

Author: Paola Galdi - AIM CISC

Abstract

Individuals managing more than one long-term condition are at a heightened risk of experiencing adverse events (AEs) such as falls, fractures, and internal bleeding. These risks arise from complex interactions between disease symptoms, medications, and individual patient characteristics, which influence the occurrence and severity of AEs. Improved anticipatory management of these factors can significantly enhance patient

Abstracts

outcomes. Most predictive models in healthcare use tabular data, which inadequately represents the complex, relational nature of medical information. A promising alternative is the utilization of knowledge graphs, which offer a flexible and integrated representation of relationships between entities. They model facts as subject-property-object triples, such as a patient (subject) having a family history of (property) a condition like osteoporosis (object).

Our proposed framework leverages a 'general-purpose' knowledge graph constructed from electronic health records. This graph serves as a foundational data structure from which multiple predictive models for different AEs can be trained. By incorporating relationships between variables and higher-order interactions directly into the model, this approach captures more nuanced patterns and dependencies in the data.

To demonstrate the utility of our approach, we use the prediction of imminent risk of hip fracture as an initial model. This serves as a proof of concept, showcasing how a knowledge graph can be applied to a specific AE prediction scenario. However, this can be customized and extended to predict various AEs across different patient populations and conditions.

The efficacy of our approach is evaluated based on three key metrics: prediction accuracy (how often the model makes an erroneous prediction), calibration (how closely the probability of an AE estimated by the model aligns with real-world occurrences), and interpretability (how easily model predictions can be explained and validated by domain experts). These metrics ensure the model performs well and provides insights that are understandable and actionable for clinicians.

Redesigning Primary Care with People with Learning Disabilities

Authors: Ellie Harvey, Alison Drewett - DECODE

Supported by Sarah Rabbitte (LD Nurse), Amy Wilkins (SALT) and our PPI members.
PIs: Professor Thomas Jun and Dr Satheesh Gangadharan

The DECODE Research Project has developed artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms which can spot 'clusters' of health conditions which commonly occur together in people with Learning Disabilities (LD), and their 'trajectories' - or the patterns of how conditions progress over time. Knowing which conditions individuals are at risk of means we can personalise their care: Predicting, preventing, and preparing them for ill-health in the future so they can live longer, independent lives.

This AI has huge potential to improve health and social care, but it's essential we design its implementation together with the professionals, carers, and service users who will benefit from it. To do this, Design Thinking offers a powerful suite of tools to stimulate creative pressure and abstract thinking to co-design solutions with stakeholders; however, many of these techniques have never been used with people with LD.

Delivering a co-design session for people with LD required careful consideration of their cognitive, communication, emotional, and practical support needs. In collaboration with our PPI members, we developed a session using Playmobil® to physically re-enact a medical appointment and engage people with LD in discussing their priorities for better primary care. This playful and enjoyable activity gave us valuable insights from an underserved population whose views are often excluded from the usual surveys. Together, we pushed beyond their frustrations with the current system and towards thinking positively and creatively about improving care. As we look to put DECODE's research into practice, accessible co-design activities can ensure people with LD are included in what the future of their healthcare might look like with AI. Their ideas were combined with the results of 6 other workshops with professionals and carers to develop 3 final 'use cases' for DECODE - personalising Annual Health Checks, better accessible health information, and strategically commissioning services.

Abstracts

Ensuring AI Models Developed in Sensitive Healthcare Data are Deployed Responsibly

Author: Lewis Hotchkiss

Abstract

The Dementias Platform UK (DPUK) Data Portal is a Trusted Research Environment (TRE) which contains multi-modal data from over 3.5 million subjects. Over the past year we have seen a rapid increase in AI applications to develop models, some of which have potential for clinical implementation into health services. To enable the safe development and deployment of these models, we have had to develop our governance and practices to ensure models protect the privacy of the individuals data that is being used to train them. We were funded by DARE UK to establish an AI Risk Community Group to host a series of workshops with members of the public (to gather their concerns with using their health data in AI), AI researchers (to understand how they felt implement Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs) into their research), and with data owners (to understand their ability to assess the risk of AI models using their data). From the results gathered from these workshops, we developed a comprehensive framework, governance and guidelines for the development and release of safe AI in sensitive healthcare data. To enable models to be implemented into practice, ensuring privacy is an essential aspect to allow this to happen, especially when data comes from secure environments. These guidelines and assessment framework allow us to confidently assess the risk of AI models being deployed/released and means we can now comfortably allow AI research in the Data Portal. We worked closely with members of the public to achieve this to ensure their concerns and suggestions are put at the centre of this framework.

Identifying Clusters and Trajectories of MLTCs in People with ID using Machine Learning Approaches

Authors: Rania Kousovista, Emeka Abakasanga, Georgina Cosma, Vasa Curcin, Gyuchan, Thomas Jun, Satheesh Kumar Gangadharan - DECODE

Abstract

Identifying and understanding the co-occurrence of multiple long-term conditions (MLTCs) in individuals with intellectual disabilities (ID) is crucial for effective healthcare management. People with ID often face significant challenges due to the high prevalence of MLTCs, which complicates their health outcomes and requires specialised care strategies. This research focuses on applying advanced machine learning techniques to identify clusters and trajectories of MLTCs within this vulnerable population, aiming to enhance healthcare coordination and outcomes. The study utilises comprehensive data from two independent sources: the Clinical Practice Research Datalink (CPRD), comprising 22018 adults with ID in England, and the Secure Anonymised Information Linkage (SAIL) Databank, covering 14323 adults with ID in Wales, from 2000 onwards. The data include a range of primary care, secondary care, social, and mortality records. Our methodology encompasses several critical steps: identifying and mitigating bias in patient data, detecting significant clusters of MLTCs, and developing trajectories of these conditions using machine learning models. These models reveal temporal patterns, identify conflicts and overlaps in clinical guidelines, and predict patient-specific outcomes. Additionally, the research models key risk factors and health events, such as mortality and hospitalisation, to provide a comprehensive understanding of the health risks faced by individuals with ID. The final output of this research is a user-friendly tool designed to facilitate population-level data modelling and analysis. This tool is intended to assist healthcare professionals in predicting and managing MLTCs more effectively, leading to better personalised care strategies.

This research contributes to the broader goal of leveraging Artificial Intelligence to improve healthcare coordination for individuals with ID by understanding which conditions are more likely to co-occur and how they progress over time. Ultimately, this will enhance the quality of life of people with ID and reduce healthcare disparities.

Abstracts

Evaluating the effect of intention-to-treat static treatment strategies and per-protocol sustained dynamic treatment strategies for deprescribing anti-platelet and/or anticoagulant therapy in a population with polypharmacy and multimorbidity.

Authors: Maurice M O'Connell, Matthew Sperrin, The DynAIRx Project collaborators

Evaluating the effect of a treatment strategy on clinical outcomes under a causal inference framework, necessitates the comparison of outcomes under different courses of action. For example, in a population with both polypharmacy (individuals on five or more medications) and multimorbidity (two or more conditions), to quantify the effect of deprescribing anti-platelet therapy on stroke and bleeding outcomes, the outcomes could be compared between a group of patients on anti-platelets who stop them, versus a group who continue to take them, when time zero and the start and end of follow-up are clearly defined. In the absence of randomised controlled trials (RCT) for deprescribing, questions about the safety and comparative effectiveness can be emulated under a target trial framework using large observational datasets. We outline a causal framework for the emulation of sequential target trials of deprescribing certain medications (e.g. anti-platelets, anti-coagulants) in people with polypharmacy and multi-morbidity by clearly defining our causal estimand (eligibility criteria, treatment strategies, treatment assignment, the start and end of follow-up, outcomes, causal contrasts) and the data analysis plan. We consider both intention-to-treat static treatment strategies and per-protocol effects under sustained dynamic treatment strategies as well as joint effects of deprescribing more than one medication (e.g. anti-platelets and/or anti-coagulants). Counterfactual theory is used in a way that avoids common methodologic pitfalls. Causal machine learning is considered to make use of flexible data-adaptive machine learning procedures which aim to reduce the need to make assumptions that the model is correct and a priori specified. Doubly robust approaches attempt to overcome model misspecification when at least one model is correct. Explicit target trial emulation alone cannot eliminate the bias that arises from lack of randomisation and estimand misspecification but the framework can help to provide a structure to clearly define causal estimands.

 This abstract was selected for a lightning talk by the Conference Programme Committee

A novel approach to making predictions from electronic healthcare records using Temporal Graph Convolutional Neural Networks (TGCNNs)

Authors: Samuel D. Relton, Zoe Hancox, Asra Aslam - DynAIRx

Current methods for predicting patient outcomes using electronic healthcare records (EHRs) often rely on logistic regressions, which fail to capture the sequence of clinical events, or recurrent neural networks (RNNs), which capture the order but not the timing between events.

In the DynAIRx project, we introduce a novel approach that leverages both the sequence and timing of events to maximise predictive power. Our method involves representing EHRs as temporal graphs to identify patterns that are predictive of poor patient outcomes. We call this approach a Temporal Graph Convolutional Neural Network (TGCNN). The TGCNN architecture uniquely integrates temporal information and graph-based learning to capture complex dependencies between clinical events.

Applying TGCNN to predict the need for hip replacements in a cohort of 140,000 primary care patients, we achieved state-of-the-art performance with an AUC of 0.72 and an AUPRC of 0.19. In comparison, an LSTM model achieved an AUC of 0.70 and an AUPRC of 0.14. Additionally, we adapted explainability methods such as GRAD-CAM to highlight the most influential parts of the patient record for our predictions. Our TGCNN approach also facilitates clustering of patient trajectories to identify indicative pathways.

Abstracts

A novel approach to making predictions from electronic healthcare records using Temporal Graph Convolutional Neural Networks (TGCNNs) (*continued*)

Authors: Samuel D. Relton, Zoe Hancox, Asra Aslam - DynAIRx

This poster summarises our team's current work on this methodology and outlines its future applications within the DynAIRx project: targeting structured medication reviews to those at highest need by predicting the likelihood of hospital admission and adverse drug reactions. Our explainability methods can help clinicians prepare for a structured medication review, by highlighting key parts of the patient record where they can focus their attention.

Interdisciplinary entanglements: emergence of ideas, consensus and technologies in scientific practice.

Authors: Duncan J Reynolds, Deborah Swinglehurst, Megan Clinch - AI Multiply

Abstract

A central assumption of the NIHR Artificial Intelligence for Multiple Long-term Conditions (AIM) funding call is that bringing together clinicians, data scientists and social scientists will enable more comprehensive understandings of multiple long-term conditions trajectories. But how is this achieved in practice?

As social scientists we are studying the work of the AI-Multiply consortium from within, examining how interdisciplinary collaborations involving AI and health professionals proceed and what constitutes success. We are building a rich, critical analysis of how a new AI-in-health technology is brought about, fostering opportunities for reflexive learning, and sharing our ongoing analyses across the consortium to support thoughtful interdisciplinary AI-in-health conversations. Our overarching research question is: How do interdisciplinary teams work collaboratively to create ideas, make decisions, negotiate disagreement and build consensus? To date we have conducted: 144 hours of ethnographic observations of management, technical, clinical, patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) activities, including interdisciplinary project meetings; 19 interviews with consortia members; three pan-consortium reflexive workshops. We are building a rich picture of how the work is done, how project actors make sense of the work they are engaged in, and what is being accomplished. We are drawing on social theory as we explore three emergent foci of analytic interest: 1) How AI is 'made explainable' within and between different teams. 2) How ethical conundrums are navigated in practice. 3) The creation of boundary objects to sustain and enable interdisciplinary work. Our work shows how diverse norms, values and dispositions are collectively managed and become sedimented within emerging AI-algorithms.

 This abstract was selected for a lightning talk by the Conference Programme Committee

Probabilistic Modelling of Onset Times (ProMOTe)

Author: Kieran Richards - AI Multiply

Abstract

The co-occurrence of multiple long-term conditions (MLTC), or multimorbidity, in an individual can reduce their lifespan and severely impact their quality of life. Understanding how these conditions develop together over time can help us identify the genetic and environmental factors involved, and potentially identify individuals who may benefit from early targeted intervention.

Abstracts

In our research, we introduce a new method called Probabilistic Modelling of Onset Times (ProMOTe) that helps group and predict the progression of these conditions. Unlike existing methods, ProMOTe is able to handle incomplete or uncertain information, which is often overlooked.

We analysed data from 150,000 people in the UK Biobank and discovered 50 distinct patterns in how diseases tend to develop together. These patterns not only align with findings from recent studies but also demonstrate the power of AI to uncover hidden insights in complex health data. Furthermore, by predicting future health trajectories based on a person's medical history, our approach holds significant potential for informing public health strategies and policy. This could lead to more targeted, early interventions, ultimately improving the lives of those living with multiple long-term conditions.

★ This abstract was selected for a lightning talk
by the Conference Programme Committee

Multimorbidity analysis with low condition counts: a robust Bayesian approach for small but important subgroups

Author: Guillermo Romero Moreno - AIM CISC

Abstract

Robustly examining associations between long-term conditions may be important in identifying opportunities for intervention in multimorbidity but is challenging when evidence is limited. We have developed a Bayesian inference framework that is robust to sparse data and used it to quantify morbidity associations in the oldest old, a population with limited available data.

We analysed associations obtained with Relative Risk (RR), a standard measure in the literature, and compared them to our proposed measure, Associations Beyond Chance (ABC). To enable a broad exploration of interactions between long-term conditions, we built networks of association and assessed differences in their analysis when associations are estimated by RR or ABC. Our Bayesian framework was appropriately more cautious in attributing association when evidence is lacking, particularly in uncommon conditions. This caution in reporting association was also present in reporting differences in associations between sex and affected the aggregated measures of multimorbidity and network representations. Incorporating uncertainty into multimorbidity research is crucial to avoid misleading findings when evidence is limited, a problem that particularly affects small but important subgroups.

Our proposed framework improves the reliability of estimations of associations and, more in general, of research into disease mechanisms and multimorbidity. In this talk, I will briefly introduce common network science approaches to multimorbidity research, present and explain our methodological approach, and present and show how our method can be easily used by the multimorbidity community via our released software package (<https://github.com/Juillermo/ABC>).

Abstracts

Exploring the Higher-Order Interactions among Multiple Long-Term Conditions

Author: Sohan Seth - AIM CISC

Abstract

Multimorbidity or Multiple Long-Term Conditions (MLTCs) refers to the presence of two or more long-term, or chronic, conditions simultaneously in an individual. Pairwise interactions among Long-Term Conditions (LTCs), commonly referred to as co-morbidities, are well explored in the literature. Pairwise interactions essentially captures whether one LTC increases the chance of the other LTC. However, interactions among multiple LTCs are less explored. For example, consider the case of three LTCs. Intuitively, the third-order interaction captures if any two LTCs together increase the chance of the remaining LTC. In this study, we explore higher-order interactions among LTCs.

We analyse a dataset of 40 LTCs and around 1.75M individuals to better understand the higher-order landscape of LTCs for up to orders order 5. We stratify the study population by 5-years age group to better understand how higher-order interactions among conditions change over age groups. We observe that there are higher-order interactions present in the dataset for different age groups and LTCs with higher-order interactions are similar over subsequent age groups. These observations have potential implications on the complexities of LTCs and their interdependencies.

AI-Driven Insights into Early-Onset Multimorbidity Clusters and Long-Term Health Trajectories: A Path Towards Improved Healthcare Planning

Authors: Mozhdeh Shiranirad, Louise Coutts, Emilia Holland, Roberta Chiovoloni, Zlatko Zlatev, Simon DS Fraser, Rebecca B Hoyle - MELD-B

Abstract

Living with multiple long-term conditions (MLTCs) significantly affects patients' lives. These effects are not only related directly to patients' health but also influence them in other ways such as financially and emotionally. This study aims to elucidate the patterns of lived experiences and the associated burden for patients with MLTCs using a data-driven approach, by analyzing electronic health record data from primary and secondary health systems. We apply artificial intelligence (AI) techniques to identify early-onset (by age 65) and burdensome MLTC clusters using routine general practitioner and hospital data. Indicators of burden are identified through qualitative evidence synthesis and a consensus study¹ (Holland, 2024). These indicators are then extracted from the Secure Anonymised Information Linkage (SAIL)² Databank to construct a framework describing patients' experiences of burden associated with living with MLTCs.

Machine learning algorithms are employed to uncover patterns and relationships among these indicators, facilitating the identification of distinct profiles of burden or health-related work experienced by patients. Cluster analysis is performed using machine learning methods specifically designed to handle the unique characteristics of routine data, including incomplete, large, and mixed-type datasets. Techniques such as extended k-means and mixture models are utilized. Beyond merely identifying MLTC clusters, we also implement explainable AI techniques to interpret the key factors contributing to the burdensomeness within each cluster. These insights provide valuable information for public health prevention efforts, healthcare planning, and resource allocation, with the potential to reduce or delay the impact of MLTCs.

Abstracts

Trajectories in long-term condition accumulation and mortality in older adults: a group-based trajectory modelling approach using the English Longitudinal Study of Ageing

Authors: Glenn Simpson, Christos V Chalitsios, Cornelia Santoso, Yvonne Nartey, Nusrat Khan, Nazrul Islam, Beth Stuart, Andrew Farmer, Hajira Dambha-Miller - Cluster-AIM

Objectives

To classify older adults into clusters based on accumulating long-term conditions (LTC) as trajectories, characterise clusters and quantify their associations with all-cause mortality.

Design

We conducted a longitudinal study using the English Longitudinal Study of Ageing over 9 years (n=15,091 aged 50 years and older). Group-based trajectory modelling was used to classify people into clusters based on accumulating LTC over time. Derived clusters were used to quantify the associations between trajectory memberships, sociodemographic characteristics and all-cause mortality by conducting regression models.

Results

Five distinct clusters of accumulating LTC trajectories were identified and characterised as: 'no LTC' (18.57%), 'single LTC' (31.21%), 'evolving multimorbidity' (25.82%), 'moderate multimorbidity' (17.12%) and 'high multimorbidity' (7.27%). Increasing age was consistently associated with a larger number of LTCs. Ethnic minorities (adjusted OR=2.04; 95% CI 1.40 to 3.00) were associated with the 'high multimorbidity' cluster. Higher education and paid employment were associated with a lower likelihood of progression over time towards an increased number of LTCs. All the clusters had higher all-cause mortality than the 'no LTC' cluster.

Conclusions

The development of multimorbidity in the number of conditions over time follows distinct trajectories. These are determined by non-modifiable (e.g., age, ethnicity) and modifiable factors (e.g., education and employment). Stratifying risk through clustering will enable practitioners to identify older adults with a higher likelihood of worsening LTC over time to tailor effective interventions to prevent mortality.

Co-production of a stakeholder workshop to inform multimorbidity prevention research: working with public contributors to ask the right questions (The MELD-B experience)

Authors: S Stannard, R Wilkinson, JK Gill, J McMahon, J Welch, SDS Fraser, NA Alwan - MELD-B

Corresponding author: S Stannard (S.J.Stannard@soton.ac.uk)

Introduction:

The MELD-B project aims to identify childhood lifecourse targets for the prevention of early-onset, burdensome multimorbidity, and to characterise 'burden' for people living with multimorbidity. Drawing upon lived experiences and the expertise of policy and practice stakeholders can enrich implementation of the MELD-B project, steer academic analysis, and contribute to meaningful and practical outcomes and outputs. In pursuit of this collaborative approach, a stakeholder workshop, co-produced with PPIE members, was conducted to inform the MELD-B project.

Abstracts

Methods:

PPIE members co-produced the planning of the workshop, including the utilisation of a project-specific animation and the creation of imaginary persona. 25 stakeholders from backgrounds including integrated care boards, healthcare practitioners, academics, council employees and non-for-profit organisations attended the two-hour workshop. The workshop aimed to identify -based on the experience and expertise of the stakeholders- critical time points and targets in the early life course (from before pregnancy up until 18 years), for feasible and practical interventions to prevent or delay multimorbidity. The stakeholders were split into three groups facilitated by two team members and Jamboard (an online interactive whiteboard) was used to collate ideas.

Findings:

A number of focus areas emerged that will inform future research on utilising longitudinal data for the early life course prevention of multimorbidity. Firstly, priority candidates included: mental health, educational attainment and attendance, the early identification of conditions and neurodiversity, the role of diet and nutrition, and wider family factors. Important timepoints for interventions included transitional ages such as the start of primary and secondary school, and the very early lifecourse (pre-primary school). Later adolescence was considered a less important timepoint than these earlier timepoints.

Interpretations:

Successful implementation of a co-produced stakeholder workshop has led to the identification of priority candidates and important timepoints that will inform the choice of variables analysed in the MELD-B project.

Authors contributions:

All authors supported the planning of the stakeholder workshop. SS, NA, JG and RW conducted the stakeholder workshop. SS drafted the summary report and NA drafted the accompanying figure. SS and NA produced the first draft of the abstract. All authors reviewed the abstract and approved the final draft.

Exploring the Relationship Between Risk Scores for Five Early Life Domains and Odds of Obesity and Hypertension Comorbidity: Findings from the 1970 The British Cohort Study (BCS70)

Authors: S Stannard, A Berrington, N Ziauddeen, RK Owen, SDS Fraser, S Paranjothy, RB Hoyle, N A Alwan - MELD-B

Keywords: Early-life, obesity, hypertension

Abstract

Background: For outcomes such as obesity and hypertension, determinants are likely to be complex and multidimensional. Therefore, to design realistic interventions, epidemiological research should incorporate information from multiple risk exposure domains to assess the effect on health. In this paper we explore risk scores for five early life domains and odds of obesity and hypertension comorbidity.

Abstracts

Methods

We used data from 17,196 participants in the 1970 British Cohort Study. The outcome was obesity (BMI of ≥ 30) and hypertension (blood pressure $>140/90$ mm Hg or self-reported doctor's diagnosis) comorbidity at age 46. Early life domains included: 'prenatal, antenatal, neonatal and birth', 'developmental attributes and behaviour', 'child education and academic ability', 'socioeconomic factors' and 'parental and family environment'. Stepwise backward elimination selected variables for inclusion for each domain. Predicted risk scores of obesity and hypertension for each cohort member within each domain were calculated. Logistic regression investigated the association between domain-specific risk scores and odds of obesity-hypertension, controlling for demographic factors and other domains.

Results

In unadjusted models, higher domain-specific risk scores were associated with increased odds of obesity-hypertension comorbidity. In adjusted analyses, higher domain-specific risk scores remained associated with increased odds of obesity-hypertension comorbidity, with the strongest associations to the parental and family environment domain (OR 1.11 95%CI 1.05-1.18) and the socioeconomic factors domain (OR 1.11 95%CI 1.05-1.17).

Conclusions

Appropriate modelling choices of combined effects of early-life risk factors need to be explored and tested. Targeted prevention interventions aimed at population groups with shared early-life characteristics could have an impact on cardiovascular risk in adulthood.

Main messages: Targeted prevention interventions aimed at population groups with shared early-life characteristics could have an impact on obesity-hypertension prevalence.

Exploring the Relationship Between Education and Academic Ability in Childhood and Number of Hospital Admissions and Outpatient Appointments in Adulthood: Findings from the Aberdeen Children of the 1950's (ACONF)

Authors: S Stannard, SDS Fraser, R Owen, A Berrington, S Paranjothy, N A Alwan - MELD-B

Background

Outpatient appointments and hospital admissions represents one aspect of burden for those living with multiple long-term conditions. Yet the relationship between factors in childhood and number of appointments and admissions has yet to be explored. In this paper we explored the association between education and academic ability in childhood and the reporting of both outpatient appointments and hospital admissions in adulthood, accounting for the mediating role of adult factors.

Method

The analytical sample consisted of 7183 participants in the Aberdeen Children of the 1950's Cohort. Three outcomes measured over a five year period (2004-2008) included: five or more outpatient appointments, two or more hospital admissions, and three or more outpatient appointments and one or more hospital admission. The exposure was a domain focusing on education and academic ability in childhood (age 6-11). Stepwise backward elimination selected variables for inclusion within the domain. Predicted risk scores of the three outcomes for each cohort member were calculated. Logistic regression investigated the association between domain predicted risk score and odds of the three outcomes controlling for confounders. In multivariate models we considered the mediating role of self-reported long-term condition and adult mediators recorded between 2001-2003.

Abstracts

Result

Adjusting for confounders, higher predicted risk values were associated with outpatient appointments, hospital admissions and combined outpatient appointments and hospital admissions. Considering the mediating role of long-term conditions, associations remained but odds ratios were reduced. After adjusting for other adult mediators, higher predicted risk values remained associated to combined outpatient appointments and hospital admissions.

Conclusions

Education and academic ability in early life may be related to hospital admission and outpatient appointments in adulthood independently from the number of long-term conditions. However, these relationship may operate through adult mediators including the age at which the cohort members left education.

Practice-level variability for prevalence of polypharmacy and potentially inappropriate prescribing

Author: Muhammad Usman - OPTIMAL

Abstract

This study explores the practice-level variability FOR PREVALENCE OF POLYPHARMACY AND POTENTIALLY INAPPROPRIATE PRESCRIBING for all registered patients aged 18 years or above on 31st December 2021 in Tayside and Fife, Scotland. Each of the 637,599 patients was assessed for the presence of Multiple Long-Term Conditions (MLTC), Polypharmacy, Frailty, and Scottish Therapeutic Utility (STU) indicators. We reported the prevalence of MLTC, polypharmacy, therapeutic indicators and Frailty across age groups, sex, and Scottish Index of Deprivation. In younger age-group, the prevalence of MLTC and sever Frailty was found to be 1.6% and 0.8%, respectively. In contrast, these conditions were significantly more frequent in the older age group, with prevalence rates of 57.6% for MLTC and 8.7% for severe Frailty. Furthermore, we analysed that the prevalence of polypharmacy and STU indicators in the younger age group was 7.8% and 0.04%, respectively. However, these figures increased significantly in the older age-group, with 37.9% for polypharmacy use and 11.5% for STU indicators. Polypharmacy was more frequent particularly in females in deprived areas, who also were more likely to have POTENTIALLY INAPPROPRIATE PRESCRIBING measured by STU indicators. Practice-level variability was observed in polypharmacy and STU indicators. In our analysis, 16.5% of practices had polypharmacy levels above the prediction interval, while 18.2% exceeded the prediction interval for STU indicators. On the other hand, 20% and 24.3% of practices had polypharmacy and STU indicator levels below the prediction interval, respectively. This variability highlights the need for tailored interventions to address inconsistencies in clinical practice.

Engaging people with learning disabilities and their carers in conversations about Artificial Intelligence.

Authors: Amy Wilkins, Sarah Rabbitte, DECODE PPI Members, Georgina Cosma - DECODE

Abstract

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a complex and abstract concept that's becoming increasingly present in daily life. Currently, little literature exists around ways to engage public conversations about research involving AI. Researchers need to find creative ways to explain AI to a broad audience to enable them to actively participate in research.

Abstracts

Patient and Public Involvement (PPI) groups in the DECODE Research Project consisted of people with learning disability (PwLD) and carers. Experienced clinicians acting as PPI leads (a Learning Disability nurse and Speech and Language Therapist) used their skills to make the information accessible. This included simplifying language, re-wording, checking back, considering the images used and using physical items that can be seen or held.

The PPI leads found visual ways to make AI tangible so that the group could understand how DECODE's research is using AI to improve health outcomes for PwLD. These methods included: 'Who can do it better?': an activity looking at the pros and cons of machines versus humans and sorting physical items into groups to introduce the concept of clusters. Online AI tools were tried to demonstrate the breadth of tasks that AI can achieve. The complex issues of trust and bias were discussed using easy read presentations: including simple language, pictures, and relatable scenarios.

A key learning experience was judging how much people needed to understand to engage with conversations or tasks that DECODE researchers needed feedback on. PPI members didn't need to know how to write algorithms or code but they needed to understand fairness and ethical issues in DECODE's research.

PPI insights and perspectives indicate that information about AI needs to be kept relevant to the population/purpose it serves. DECODE's PPI work has shown that PwLD can and want to be included in AI discussions if given the right support.

The place effects on multimorbidity: a systematic scoping review

Authors: Chunyu Zheng, Clare MacRae, Laurence Rowley-Abel, Stella Arakelyan, Eleojo Abubakar, Chris Dibben, Bruce Guthrie, Alan Marshall, Jamie Pearce - AIM CISC

Background

Multimorbidity has emerged as a global public health challenge. Increasing work has identified varying individual- and household-level risk factors of multimorbidity; however, our understanding of how the features of place affect multimorbidity remains limited. This scoping review aims to identify the place-based risk factors of multimorbidity and to synthesise evidence on how place-based risk factors affect multimorbidity.

Methods: Following guidelines from Arksey and O'Malley (2005) and PRISMA-ScR, a predefined research strategy (<https://osf.io/bf84m>) was run across 7 major databases in 2023, with a double screening and data extraction process. English-language peer-reviewed studies exploring the relationship between place-based characteristics (from neighbourhood to region) and multimorbidity among the general population aged over 18 years old were included from 2010 to 2023.

Results

Twelve types of place-based risk factors of multimorbidity were identified from 76 out of 7,761 records. The most frequently examined place-based risk factors of multimorbidity were area-level deprivation/SES, pollution, and urbanity/rurality, with fairly consistent findings showing that people in deprived, polluted, or urbanised areas were more likely to be multimorbid, though this may vary by how multimorbidity is defined or measured. Other place-based risk factors, such as social cohesion and greenspace availability, were linked to single health conditions, but their associations with multimorbidity were underexplored. Finally, we proposed a theoretical framework linking place and multimorbidity through multiple pathways based on the synthesised evidence.

Conclusion: The enhanced understanding of how the place people live will affect multimorbidity has important policy implications, with the potential to benefit place-based public health interventions, which have proven to be effective in promoting health and reducing health inequalities. Our findings suggest that there remains only a partial understanding of how 'place' affects multimorbidity. Future studies should employ more precise measures for both place-based risk factors and multimorbidity and use longitudinal designs and analytical approaches for more causal insights.

Upcoming Events

AIM RSF Open Invitation Seminar:
2nd Tuesday of every month at 1:30pm

**Interdisciplinary Workshop for
Early Career Researchers**
23rd October in Edinburgh

Deadline to register: 12 September 2024

FUNDED BY

NIHR | National Institute for
Health and Care Research

If you require any further information or have any questions,
please don't hesitate to reach out to us at aimrsf@turing.ac.uk

THE UNIVERSITY
of EDINBURGH

The
**Alan Turing
Institute**

Population Data Science
Gwyddor Data Poblogaeth

Swansea University
Prifysgol Abertawe
Medical School
Ysgol Feddygaeth